

Herbal Approach to Mosquito Repellents: Formulation of a Cream Using Marigold, Neem and Camphor.

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Abstract:

Plant-based mosquito repellents have become popularity as a more friendly to the environment alternative to synthetic formulations, which are frequently harmful. The project focuses on the development and testing of a topical herbal cream containing *Tagetes erecta* (marigold), *Azadirachta indica* (neem), and *Cinnamomum camphora* (camphor), all of which contain bioactive ingredients with observed insect-repellent and antibacterial features. The cream the base was formulated for skin compatibility and stability. In response to the growing demand for safer and more sustainable alternatives, this study focuses on the development of a herbal mosquito repellent cream formulated from natural plant-based ingredients—marigold (*Tagetes* spp.), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), and camphor (*Cinnamomum camphora*). These ingredients were selected for their well-documented insecticidal and repellent properties. The formulation involved the extraction of active compounds using appropriate solvents, followed by incorporation into a stable emulsion-based cream. The final product was assessed for physical characteristics (texture, spreadability, pH), dermatological safety. The study highlights the potential of combining traditional herbal knowledge with modern formulation techniques to develop effective, eco-friendly mosquito repellents.

Keyword: Eco-friendly repellents, Topical cream preparation, Herbal cosmetic formulation, Plant-based insect repellent

INTRODUCTION:

Mosquitoes are the most unsafe of nature's many potentially fatal insects. Since ancient times, people have protected themselves from them using herbal remedies. Mosquitoes are among the most harmful insects in the natural world because they can cause fatal diseases like dengue, yellow fever, chikungunya, filariasis, and malaria [1-4]. Caraballo and King claimed that about 700 million individuals get infected by mosquitoes worldwide, and around one million of them die, according to Raja et al [5]. More than 1,200 children die from malaria in one day, according to a 2015 UNICEF malaria information sheet. Thus, protecting oneself from mosquito bites has been crucial from the beginning to the present [5]. The mosquito is probably the most unpleasant bloodsucking insect that humans encounter.

Many diseases, such as dengue fever, yellow fever, and malaria, are known to be spread by Anopheles, Culex, and Aedes fly species. The Zika virus, chikungunya, Japanese encephalitis, Rift Valley disease, West Nile virus, and lymphatic filariasis can also be spread by mosquitoes. An immune response takes place when mosquitoes inject their saliva into a host's bloodstream, where the antigens interact to IgG and IgE antibodies. The reactions often result in bumps, along with discomfort, itching, and redness. The mosquito's saliva also produces a seriously itchy and uncomfortable rash. In addition, mosquito bites may cause extremely painful skin irritation for those who come into contact with them and experience an allergic reaction to their saliva.[6] In the past, significant efforts were made to use polyherbal formulations to prevent diseases from being transmitted by mosquitoes. Although the fact that most mosquito repellents on the market are currently performing well for quickly keeping mosquitoes away, they are not the most effective option due to the presence of the hazardous chemical N, N-diethyl-meta-toluamide (DEET).[7]

Every year, mosquitoes infect about 700 million people, resulting in over one million deaths worldwide. We attempt to use natural herbal ingredients and essential oils with demonstrated mosquito-repelling properties, such as beeswax, camphor, neem, marigold, almond oil or coconut oil, aloe vera, and eucalyptus/lavender/citronella, to develop a safe and non-toxic formulation. Known for its insecticidal characteristics that marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) contains naturally occurring compounds like flavonoids and thiophenes that have a tendency to repel mosquitoes. Popular for its medicinal and pesticidal qualities, neem (*Azadirachta indica*) includes azadirachtin, a substance that effectively repels insects by interacting with their growth and feeding habits [8]. Because of its strong fragrant features, camphor (*Cinnamomum camphora*), which has long been employed in Ayurvedic medicine, acts as a natural fumigant and mosquito repellent. A topical cream formulation containing marigold, neem, and camphor delivers a safe and efficient approach to repelling mosquitoes. An eco-friendly and secure substitute for synthetic repellents can be created by utilizing the beneficial qualities of these plant-based substances. The intent of this study is to create and assess a herbal mosquito repellent cream which includes camphor, neem, and marigold, focusing its potential as a non-toxic and sustainable alternative for traditional one repellent [8].

Marigold:

Marigold (*Tagetes* spp.) naturally repels mosquitoes with compounds like pyrethrin and thiophenes. In cream form, it offers a safe, skin-friendly, and eco-friendly alternative to chemical repellents, while also soothing and protecting the skin [9].

Neem:

Neem is a natural mosquito repellent due to its insecticidal and antimicrobial properties. Compounds like azadirachtin disrupt mosquito growth and act as deterrents, helping prevent diseases like malaria and dengue. Its anti-inflammatory and skin-soothing qualities make neem a safe, eco-friendly alternative to chemical repellents [10].

Camphor:

Camphor is a natural, biodegradable ingredient used in mosquito repellent creams for its strong aroma and insecticidal properties. It repels mosquitoes by disrupting their sensory receptors and also soothes the skin with its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects. Its long-lasting vaporization ensures continuous protection, making it an effective and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic repellents [11].

Material and Methods:

Material:

Equipment Required:

- Double Boiler or Water Bath – For controlled melting of ingredients.
- Glass Beakers or Bowls – For mixing ingredients.
- Stirring Rod or Spatula – To ensure uniform mixing.
- Measuring Scale and Pipettes – For accurate measurement of ingredients.
- Sterilized Glass Jars/Containers – For storing the final product.
- Filter Paper & Funnel – For filtering extracted oils.

Ingredients Used in Natural Mosquito Repellent Cream:

Ingredients Type	Ingredients	Quantity
Active Ingredients (Repellent Agents)	Marigold Extract/Oil	2.5ml
	Neem Oil	2.5ml
	Camphor Powder	1.25g
Base Ingredients (Cream Formation)	Beeswax	5g
	Almond Oil or Coconut Oil	7.5ml
	Aloe vera Gel	5ml
	Essential Oil (Citronella/lavender/ eucalyptus)	1,2drops

Table no.1: Ingredients Used in Natural Mosquito Repellent Cream

Extraction of Marigold Essential Oil:

1. Marigold petals were dried in the shade for 2–3 days.
2. The dried petals were ground into a coarse powder.
3. Steam distillation or ethanol (alcohol) soaking for 48 hours was used to extract the essential oil.
4. The extracted oil was filtered and stored for use.

Fig no.1.: Extraction of marigold**Procedure:****Formulation of Mosquito Repellents Cream:**

Step 1: Extraction of Marigold Essential Oil

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2. The dried petals were ground into a coarse powder.
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Step 2: Preparing the Cream Base

1. Beeswax and coconut oil were melted in a double boiler over low heat.
2. Once melted, aloe vera gel was added and mixed well.

Step 3: Adding Active Ingredients

1. The mixture was removed from heat and allowed to cool slightly (without solidifying).
2. Marigold oil, neem oil, and camphor powder were added while stirring continuously.
3. Optionally, 5 drops of essential oil (e.g., citronella or eucalyptus) were added to enhance mosquito repellent properties.

Step 4: Storing the Cream

1. The mixture was poured into sterilized glass jars or containers.
2. It was allowed to cool and solidify at room temperature.
3. The cream was stored in a cool, dark place.

Fig no.2: Formulated Cream

Evaluation Parameter and Results:

Sr no.	Evaluation	F1	F2	F3*
1.	Organoleptic property	Opaque, pale yellow, smooth	Opaque, pale yellow, smooth	Opaque, Olive Green, smooth
2.	Washability	Easy washable	Not easily washable	Easily washable
3.	Skin irritancy	Slightly irritating, after application	Non-irritating,	Non-irritating, Suitable for most skin types
4.	Homogeneity	Not homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous
5.	Spreadability	Good spreadability	Good spreadability	Even and smooth application
6.	pH	6.12	6.10	~5.5-6.5 (skin friendly)

7.	Extrudability	70	73.6	78.8
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(Based on the evaluation parameters and results presented in the above table, Batch F3 is selected as the final formulation)

Table no.2: Evaluation Parameter and Results

Evaluation Parameter:

1. Organoleptic Properties (Appearance, Odor, Texture):

Expected results: A smooth, creamy texture with a pleasant or neutral herbal aroma. It shouldn't be overly greasy or sticky.

Appearance	Smooth
Odor	Neutral Herbal aroma
Texture	Creamy

Table no.3: Organoleptic Properties (Appearance, Odor, Texture)

2. pH Level:

Assessment: Test the cream using a pH meter or pH strips.

Expected Results: A skin-friendly pH range of 4.5 to 6.5 is recommended to avoid inflammation. Neem oil and camphor can occasionally alter pH, thus balance is essential.

Fig no.3: pH Level**3. Skin Irritancy:**

Patch test sensitive skin areas, such as the inner forearm. Evaluate for redness, itching, or pain after 24 hours.

Expected results: No irritation, redness, or burning. Aloe vera and coconut/almond oil should help relieve inflammation.

Fig no3: Skin Irritancy test**4. Spreadability:**

Assess: Calculate how easily the cream distributes on the skin with little effort.

Expected results: The product should spread smoothly without leaving a significant residue. The addition of coconut/almond oil and aloe vera should improve this property.

Fig no.4: Spreadability test

5. Washability:

Assessment: Apply a tiny amount to your skin and try washing it off with water. Expected results: Moderately water-resistant yet not difficult to remove. A balance is required so that it remains effective on the skin yet can be dried off as needed.

Fig no.5: Washability

6. Extrudability (Ease of Dispensing):

Assessment: If stored in a squeeze tube or jar, check how easily the cream comes out.

Expected Results: Should be easy to dispense without excessive force. If it's too thick, adjusting the oil-to-beeswax ratio can improve this.

Mosquito Repellents Activity:

Formulation no	Parameter	Control	Test 1	Test 2
F1	Number of mosquitoes	10	10	10
	Number of mosquitos Repellents	0	05	06
	Repellents activity	No	Yes	Yes
	Observation time (min)	10	10	10
	Temperature ⁰ c	28	28	28
F2	Number of mosquitoes	10	10	10
	Number of mosquitos Repellents	0	06	08
	Repellents activity	No	Yes	Yes
	Observation time (min)	10	10	10
	Temperature ⁰ c	28	28	28
F3*	Number of mosquitoes	10	10	10
	Number of mosquitos Repellents	0	08	09
	Repellents activity	No	Yes	Yes
	Observation time (min)	10	10	10
	Temperature ⁰ c	28	28	28

Table no.4: Mosquito Repellents Activity**Fig no.6: Volunteer test for mosquito repellent Cream**

Conclusion:

The formulation of a herbal mosquito repellent cream with Marigold (*Tagetes* spp.), Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), and Camphor (*Cinnamomum camphora*) offers a possible natural alternative to synthetic repellents. The active molecules in these herbal products have strong repellent features providing beneficial mosquito protection while eliminating the risk of health risks associated with chemical-based solutions. The cream formulation was found to be skin-friendly, easy to use, and effective over time. This study demonstrates the possibility for combining traditional botanical knowledge with current formulation techniques to create safe, friendly to the environment, and cost-effective mosquito repellent actions. Further analysis on long-term stability, large-scale production, and user acceptability is needed to progress this herbal repellent to commercial use.

The findings are positive and promising. The formulation F3 had the highest repellent activity. Finally, it was discovered that oil extracts have the potential to be a mosquito repellent and can be converted into a commercial product such as an essence stick or an insect repellent lotion, etc.

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